

Design Briefing for Emotions & Meaning

Søren Ingomar Petersen

*President Ingomar & Ingomar - Consulting
South Pasadena, California, USA, soren.petersen@ingomar.net*

Abstract: Industrial Design that incorporates meaning and emotions is becoming an important strategic differentiator in offerings. Integrating these elements in the synthesis of concepts requires the upfront inclusion of these elements in the design briefing. The approach developed here is inspired by findings from psychiatry and branding. Applying Design Quantification, a matrix is constructed for systematic inclusion of meaning and emotion in the content of the design briefing. To avoid exceeding designers' cognitive abilities to synthesize concepts, an appropriate balance for inclusion of these elements is examined. An estimate of appropriate content of meaning and emotions is accomplished through auditing state-of-the-art proposals for integration opportunities. Applying Design Quantification, engineering and industrial design focused proposals are analyzed, revealing important inclusion of and co-dependencies between traditional Design Quality Criteria. The results become recommended guidelines for balancing the content in a design briefing, thereby, effectively supporting the integration of meaning and emotion in offerings.

Key words: *Design brief, design proposal, design for meaning, design for emotions, evidence-based management, Design Quantification, Design Quality Criteria.*

1. Introduction

Industrial design has now become a mature field in its own right, having evolved from designing products, to services, experiences, meaning and emotions [1]. Trends have outcompeted their predecessors, from semantics in the late 80's, lifestyle in the early 90's, branding in the mid 90's, user-centered design in the early 2000's to design thinking in the mid '2000's. Inclusion of the various components have led to the emergence of new support functions, such as anthropology, ethnographic brand management [2] and now design quantification.

1.1. Opportunity

The growing challenge is the systematic and comprehensive/evidence based integration of these processes and criteria into the overall design process, beginning with the design proposal. At the end of the day, when research is completed, data analyzed and conclusions made, the challenge remaining is for the design team and the individual designer to translate these findings into competitive offerings. Information, absent in the design concepts, is thereby relegated to having an evaluation value only [3]. Hence, the first and foremost opportunity is for the design proposal to promote an efficient and effective synthesis of elements, such as meaning and emotion. To make this happen, a thorough understanding of applying meaning and emotion together with the design briefing process is crucial.

1.2. Model: Emotions - Meaning - Design

Why do we have strong emotional reactions to some experiences, while others are perceived as lackluster? The answer can be found in how our brain interprets sensory stimulation, as filtered by our logical mind, based on our perception of meaning. Sensory input is registered in the form of: visual, auditory, tactile, temperature sense, olfactory, taste, temporal, spatial and geographically orientation of stimuli. This input causes feelings, such as pleasure and pain [4]. These feelings are then filtered by our sense of meaning, which is formed by nature and nurture and is constantly evolving as we gain new experiences. The result is the feeling of an emotion that, to a large extent, dictates our behavior. Hence, the opportunity for influencing a users product experience and behavior are inherent in their sensory contact with the offering in addition to the formation of the offerings relationship to the users sense of meaning. See Figure 1.

Figure.1: Sensory - Feeling - Meaning - Emotion: A perceptual model of the translation of sensory input into feelings. Sensory input is observed by the senses and compared to our experiences and framework of meaning. Meaning is then assigned to the experience and an emotion is produced.

1.3. Meaning - design process

Design of the sensory experience is well known, however, it is seldom systematically executed in practice. Design for meaning receives cursory attention, for the most part being based on the individual designer's personal perception of what is meaningful. The meaning behind the design is often visualized using symbols and communicated using storytelling.

How do designers discover meaning for their design concepts? Through being inspired by the design brief and from external inspirational sources, such as nature, art, fashion, movies, other products, automobiles, aviation, weapons and architecture. These sources may provide a rich diverse range of meaning, however not necessarily the ones appropriate for the business opportunity at hand.

How one can implement meaning as well as direct and manage the implementation? One such approach is through the systematic pairing of meaning and design followed by decision-making based on design quantification.

2. Procedure

The following chapter describes the framework, construction of a meaning - design model and subsequent integration of meaning considerations in the design briefing process.

2.1. Design Criteria - Meaning Model

"Men and women can endure any amount of suffering so long as they know the why to their existence." [5]. In short, that what is happening in their world has meaning. Religious institutions, in particular, the Catholic Church, are masters when it comes to ascribing meaning to life and imbedding meaning in artifacts. Commissioned by the Church, artists have translated meaning, as prescribed by the Bible, into ceremonies, buildings, clothing and accessories. In these cases, strictly guided craftsmen and not a systematic design process handled the implementation of meaning. [6] The process of industrial design is a great deal leaner than the religious integration of meaning and a systematic integration with the existing process of design becomes paramount.

2.1.1. Framework for integrating meaning in the design briefing process

There are three main forms of meaning: purpose, love and courage [7], which can be further divided into fifteen general and globally valid, subsets of meanings [8]. Applying the Inspirational Design Briefing framework [3] for design briefing to categorize meaning, results in a 15 by 9 matrix. Further restricting the focus to the Design Quality Criteria, which directly affects the user, will lead to the following 15 by 5 matrix. See Table 1.

Table 1. Meaning - Design Quality Criteria, operating with a reduced set of criteria.

			Social	Environmental	Process	Function	Expression
Purpose	Social	Accomplishment					
		Duty					
		Community					
	Adaptability	Creation					
		Enlightenment					
		Wonder					
Love	Social	Harmony					
		Justice					
		Oneness					
		Redemption					
		Truth					
	Validation						
Health	Beauty						
Courage	Social	Freedom					
	Adaptability	Security					

The devised framework visually describes the opportunities for the integration of elements of meaning into the current Inspirational Design Briefing process.

2.1.2 Example BMW - Toyota

To illustrate the different opportunities for incorporation of meaning into products, we apply the Meaning - Design Quality Criteria model to two automotive companies' compact vehicles offerings. The BMW 3 Series and the Toyota Prius. See Figure 2.

Figure 2. Visual Comparison of BMW and Toyota. BMW 3 Series Sedan six-cylinder combustion engine and Toyota Prius four-cylinder hybrid.

The BMW 3 Series Sedan is a sports sedan, positioning itself as the ultimate driving machine for cultivated, dynamic and challenging drivers. The Toyota Prius, on the other hand, is a hybrid appealing to responsible environmentally conscious family oriented drivers. A cursory mapping, by an automotive designer with fifteen years experience, of the type of meaning opportunities pursued is illustrated in Table 2.

Table 2. BMW 3 Series and Toyota Prius Meaning - Design Quality Criteria mapping. Toyota displays a denser inclusion of meaning along Social/Human and Environmental meaning, while BMW relies more on expression criteria.

Meaning: Automobile - BMW 3 Series				Meaning: Automobile - Toyota Prius			
				Social/Human	Environmental	Function	Expression
Purpose	Social	Accomplishment	x		x	x	
		Duty					
		Community	x		x	x	
Adaptability		Creation			x	x	
		Enlightenment				x	
		Wonder			x	x	
Love	Social	Harmony					
		Justice					
		Oneness			x	x	
		Redemption					
		Truth					
		Validation	x		x	x	
Health	Beauty			x	x		
Courage	Social	Freedom			x	x	
	Adaptability	Security	x		x	x	
Purpose	Social	Accomplishment	x	x	x	x	
		Duty	x	x		x	
		Community	x	x	x	x	
Adaptability		Creation				x	
		Enlightenment	x	x	x	x	
		Wonder				x	
Love	Social	Harmony			x		
		Justice	x				
		Oneness	x		x	x	
		Redemption	x	x			
		Truth					
		Validation	x				
Health	Beauty					x	
Courage	Social	Freedom				x	
	Adaptability	Security	x		x	x	

Comparing the two matrixes illustrates how Toyota has extended the meaning provided within the Social/Human and Environmental context. Notice the model illustrates focus, not qualitative differences in the respective treatment of the meaning - design criteria opportunity.

The Design Quality Criteria - Meaning model can be used for searching opportunities for integrating meaning into an offering as well as comparing proposed concepts and benchmarking of these against competitors. The extent, to which meaning can be included in the design briefing, without compromising other vital design aspects, is the topic of the second half of this study.

2.2. Balancing Design Quality Criteria and Meaning & Emotions elements

Effective and efficient synthesis of design concepts has been found to correspond to specific design proposal content and formulation. Proposal extensiveness and the content distribution of Design Quality Criteria are indicators of overall project management financial performance and reflect process control [3].

2.2.1. Study of design proposals

In evaluating performance characteristics of design proposals, regarding how design for meaning and emotions could be included, we decided to use the approach from a recent study on how to improve the design briefing process [3]. Ensuring a broad evaluation of design briefing, an engineering/functionality as well as design/formgebung perspective of design proposals was performed. This was accomplished by comparing proposals from Stanford Mechanical Engineering ME310 one-year sponsored engineering design projects (N=30) with findings from a recent study of thirty industrial design consultancies (N=30) [3]. In the design consulting study, proposals were coded using the Design Quality Criteria and proposal extensiveness/length was measured using the number of words in the proposal. The objective was to examine if the focus of the proposals related to project performance and offered an opportunity for optimization and integration of meaning. The study examined:

- 1) Comparison of sponsored engineering design and consulting industrial design projects
 - a) Proposal length
 - b) Proposal Design Quality Criteria profile
 - c) Relationships between Design Quality Criteria for ME and ID projects

- 2) General design proposal characteristics
 - a) Relationships between Design Quality Criteria and budget adherence
 - b) Exploring optimal combination of Process, Function and Expression

2.2.2. Findings

1.a. Proposal length

When first comparing proposal length, as measured by the number of words used, sponsored projects showed to be considerably shorter than the proposals for the design consultancies [3]. Closer examination however revealed that the sponsored project omitted significant portions of the design process description found in consulting projects. This difference could be explained by the proposals being written in the context of the design process of the course ME310, dictating the project schedule and phases. Adjusting the brief sponsored project proposals for this, revealed the length of the projects descriptions to be the same, approximately 1000 words. The only difference between the two samples length being that the sponsored projects had a slightly higher standard deviation.

1.b. Proposal Design Quality Criteria profile

With the proposals having the same length, the question was if the proposals content distribution of the sponsored projects and the design consultancies were similar [3]. Applying Design Quality Criteria analysis, revealed significant differences along the Performance criteria: Process, Function and Expression. This difference was expected, since the sponsored projects had an engineering (ME) emphasis, while the consulting projects had an industrial design (ID) emphasis. Along the overall criteria Philosophy and Context, the two samples were identical. See Figure 3.

Figure 3. Strategy - Context. Comparison of Strategy and Context content, as measured by the number of words, for sponsored engineering design and industrial design consulting projects.

Further analysis of the Strategy and Context sub-criteria revealed that the two proposal samples had the same content profiles, which offered the opportunity of treating the two samples as representative data for mechanical engineering and industrial design focused proposals. The proposals written by experienced professional proposal writers, gearing their proposals towards ID and ME, show not to discern between writing proposals for corporate sponsored projects and the design consulting industry.

1.c. Relationship between Design Quality Criteria for ME and ID projects

Displaying the sponsored projects' proposals on Functional and Expressional focus, revealed two groupings. One were projects with a focus on Function, while another was focusing on Expression, see Figure 4.

Figure 4: Function – Expression. Sponsored projects’ proposal content of Functional and Expressional criteria, as measured by the number of words used, show two distinct groupings, with one group focusing on Expression (ID characteristic) and one group focusing on Functionality (ME characteristic).

This distinct grouping of Functional ME directed and ID Expression directed proposals allowed for comparison of engineering proposals with an ID or ME focus, with industrial design proposals showing only an ID focus.

Displaying ME and ID focused proposals content along Functional and Expressional content versus Process content showed ME proposals to have a high negative linear correlation of $\text{corr.} = -0.85$ ($p < 0.05$) between Function and Process, while the ID focused proposals show medium correlation ($\text{corr.} = -0.46$, $p < 0.05$) between Expression and Process. See Figure 5.

Figure 5. Process (Function, Expression). Process as a function of Function (N=8) and Process as a function of Expression (N=11), for sponsored projects’ proposal content of Functional and Expressional criteria.

These findings are remarkable, since the recent consulting proposal study [3] shows a strong negative correlation between Expression and Process and medium between Function and Process. Once more showing that corporate sponsored ME310 proposals are equivalent to industry proposals. A linear tradeoff, or lack thereof, between Function and Expression with Process, indicates that industrial design proposals master the balancing of Expression and Process, however less so the tradeoff between Function and Process. While engineering proposals master balancing Function and Process and, to a lesser extent, the tradeoff between Expression and Process. This strongly suggests that proposals need to contain a balanced combination of Function and Expression to successfully brief a team of engineering and industrial designers, advocating co-creation of proposals.

2.b. Exploring optimal combinations of Process, Function and Expression

The apparent importance of a balanced combination of Process, Function and Expression design quality criteria begs two questions. Which combination of design quality criteria is conducive to effective and efficient concept synthesis? Secondly, how will this focus change when it includes designing for meaning and can this be accomplished without compromising existing design synthesis and/or designers cognitive abilities?

The recent study of proposals from design consulting [3], addresses budget control, an indicator of design process management. Displaying Process and Expression content in the proposals, as related to the projects subsequent profitability, shows profitable projects to have a stronger emphasis on Expression criteria over Process criteria. Applying Pareto’s 80/20-rule suggests, that for good design project management, Expression criteria content has to contribute over 10 percent of the proposal content. At approximately 25 percent contribution, project financial performance radically improves. See Figure 6.

Figure 6. Budget performance: Industrial design proposals relationship between Process, Expression, budget size and whether project is on or over budget. Size of bubble indicates budget size of proposal.

To manage design concept synthesis well, proposals from design consulting [3] show that a focus on Strategy and Context criteria within the 10 percent range is required. Focus on Process criteria needs to be in the 65 – 80 percent range, Function criteria requires about 5 percent and Expression is in the 25 percent range. With meaning being defined by Social/Human, Environmental, Function and Expression criteria, assigning development of meaning to the design process may not be cognitively feasible. Upfront definition of Expression criteria is more project efficient than relegating this to the Process criteria. If synthesis of meaning is as cognitively taxing as synthesis of Expression criteria, there may simply not be adequate proposal Process criteria content scope available to address meaning. This would suggest that the meaning of offerings be planned for in a business and design strategy phase and modeled as advanced concepts.

The use of advanced concepts is not foreign in America. For the past sixty years, American automotive manufactures have used Concept Cars to explore directions and test consumer acceptance, before launching commercial vehicle projects. This study suggests that pre-development, advanced concepts are essential for the integration of new meanings in product offerings. This offers not only the early gauging of user acceptance, but also increases budgetary control in subsequent product development phases.

4. Conclusion

This research offers a method for integrating considerations of meaning into product offerings, using the Meaning - Design Quality Criteria model.

Subsequent Design Quality Criteria analysis of design proposals and the following projects budgetary success reveals certain patterns indicative of successful project management performance. Engineering design-focused projects with a linear tradeoff between Function and Process criteria, show efficient project control. Industrial design focused projects, with a linear tradeoff between Expression and Process criteria also show efficient project control. To achieve good industrial design process management and hence profitability, a focus on Expression above 25 percent is desirable.

Observed information content distribution patterns in proposals suggests insufficient cognitive scope for synthesis of meaning when using Strategy and Context criteria that require 10 percent attention, with Process criteria 65 – 80 percent attention, Function criteria at about 5 percent and Expression in the 25 percent range attention. Therefore, meaning in offerings is best addressed upfront, before the design process begins, thus requiring less concept-meaning exploration.

The study is not yet scientifically conclusive and further research is required to establish the exact nature of the relationship between Social/Human, Environmental, Function and Expression in deliberately integrating meaning in offerings. As part of the Stanford Persuasive Technology Lab - ingomar&ingomar consulting collaboration, our intent is to further explore the findings on extreme case Peace Innovation projects by conducting simultaneous double blind conceptual design projects in late 2010.

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